

Statistical analysis plan (SAP)

enigma

Early cerebral **ImaGing** Markers of unhealthy lifestyles in Adolescents (EnIGMA)

Principal Investigator: Rodrigo Fernández Jiménez

Centro Nacional de Investigaciones Cardiovasculares

Calle de Melchor Fernández Almagro, 3, 28029, Madrid, Spain

rodrigo.fernandez@cnic.es

Co-investigators: Miriam García-Cocera^a, Carlos Real^a, Álvaro Navarro Guzmán^{ab}, Rocío Párraga^a, Jesús Martínez-Gómez^a.

Main collaborators: Gloria Santos-Beneit, Amaya de Cos-Gandoy, Patricia Bodega, Mercedes de Miguel, Javier Sánchez-González, Alberto Fernández-Pena^a.

^aCentro Nacional de Investigaciones Cardiovasculares, Madrid, Spain

^bPhillips Healthcare, Madrid, Spain.

Date and version of the document: oct 23,2024. Version 1.

Table of contents

1	Introduction	4
2	Study hypothesis and objectives.....	6
2.1	Hypothesis	6
2.2	Objectives	6
3	Study design and methods.....	7
3.1	Study design.....	7
3.2	Magnetic resonance imaging acquisition protocol.....	10
3.3	Magnetic resonance imaging post-processing	11
3.4	Cardiovascular health assessment during follow-up.....	13
3.4.1	Diet	13
3.4.2	Physical activity	14
3.4.3	Nicotine exposure.....	14
3.4.4	Sleep health	15
3.4.5	Body mass index	15
3.5	Emotional state assessment.....	15
3.5.1	Self-esteem	16
3.5.2	Mood	16
4	Data Analysis.....	17
4.1	Outcomes or dependent variables	17
4.2	Independent variables	18
4.3	Analysis method	19
4.3.1	Regions-based analysis.....	20
4.3.2	Voxel-based analysis	22
5	Acknowledgement.....	24
6	References	25

1 Introduction

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is the leading cause of death and disability, largely because of risk factors modifiable by changes in behaviour (1). However, those cardiovascular risk factors (CVRF) are not only related to CVD, but also to other relevant diseases such as neurodegenerative diseases (2,3). Bearing in mind that neurodegenerative diseases are frequently difficult to manage, identifying and reducing modifiable risk factors is essential to prevent their development. Several studies have demonstrated a relationship between cardiovascular risk factors and brain structural and functional imaging changes, assessed by magnetic resonance (MR), in people with no clinical manifestations of either cardiovascular or cerebrovascular disease (4–6). Reductions in whole-brain volume, grey matter volume and global and regional cerebral blood flow are the main observed changes, as well as an increase in cerebrospinal fluid volume and white matter hyperintensities (4). Moreover, it seems to be an association between these imaging changes and worst midlife cognitive performance, cognitive impairment and risk of dementias(7,8). Subclinical brain changes in MRI have been also associated to emotional disorders in adolescents (9,10), nevertheless there are not studies relating neuroimaging subclinical variants and emotional status in healthy adolescents. Modifiable CVRF start to be relevant in childhood and adolescence and the global prevalence of ideal healthy behaviours are already very low among adolescents (11,12). However, there is a lack of evidence about the prevalence of subclinical neuroimaging changes in this group of age. Thus, the EnIGMA (Early Imaging Markers of unhealthy lifestyles in Adolescents) project seeks to identify early adverse subclinical brain changes in adolescents and their association with different lifestyle patterns, health factors and emotional status.

The purpose of this document is to provide a detailed description of the statistical analysis plan for the brain variables of EnIGMA study. It is intended that the results reported in

the main paper will follow the principles set out in this document and these guidelines will be followed, as closely as possible, when analysing and reporting the study. However, the final analysis may be determined by unpredictable aspects of the data and this statement will be updated if necessary.

2 Study hypothesis and objectives

2.1 Hypothesis

Unhealthy lifestyles and negative emotional state in adolescents may induce subclinical brain changes that can be detected by advanced MR imaging. In contrast, those adolescents showing healthy lifestyle patterns will not show such abnormal findings.

2.2 Objectives

The overall objective of the project is to evaluate in adolescents the impact of unhealthy lifestyles and negative emotional state on early subclinical brain features that can be detected by advanced MR imaging. The scope of the study is divided into two main objectives:

1. To assess the cumulative effect of lifestyles throughout the adolescence on subclinical changes in cerebral structure and perfusion in a cohort of participants with no known neurological or cardiovascular disease.
2. To identify the association between cerebral structure and perfusion subclinical changes assessed by MR imaging and emotional state in a cohort of participants with no known emotional disorders.

These objectives will be evaluated from two different points of view. The first will be based on the assessment of pre-established anatomical brain regions. These regions represent global volumetry and perfusion variables that have been related to the effects of cardiovascular risk factor in previous studies (5,6). The second will involve conducting a voxel-wise analysis of differences in cerebral blood flow associated to emotional and Cardiovascular Health (CVH) patterns, with all MR images registered into a common anatomical space.

3 Study design and methods

3.1 *Study design*

This observational study took advantage of a cluster-randomized trial (NCT03504059) to conduct the recruitment of participants. This trial included 24 public secondary schools in Spain, encompassing 1326 adolescents (13,14). A detailed analysis of their CVH status at enrolment can be found elsewhere (12). Briefly, this study was designed as a cluster randomized controlled trial to test the effect of a comprehensive lifestyle program on the CVH of adolescents aged 12 to 16 years in Spain (**Figure 1**). The trial was launched September 2017 and finalized July 2021. Cluster units were public schools that were located in the metropolitan areas of Madrid and Barcelona.

Schools that agreed to participate were randomly allocated 1:1:1 to receive a comprehensive educational program through a long-term (4-year) intervention, a short term (2-year) intervention, or the standard curriculum. CVH was defined at 3 time points (baseline, 2-year follow-up and 4-year follow-up) using medical devices and/or self-report questionnaires. The primary results of this trial can be found elsewhere (14). Overall, the tested school-based health promotion strategies in this randomized clinical trial had a neutral effect on the CVH of the adolescents (14). Although there was evidence of a marginal beneficial effect at a point halfway through implementation in the long-term intervention group, such a benefit was not noted at 4 years (14) .

Figure 1. Design of The SI! Program for Secondary Schools trial. CVH indicates cardiovascular health. Published in JAMA Cardiol. 2023;8:816. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamacardio.2023.2231>

For inclusion in the EnIGMA project, adolescents needed to be enrolled in the cited trial and attend one of the 7 schools in the study located in the Madrid region as of December 2020. Exclusion criteria were general contraindications for a MR examination (pacemakers, cochlear implants, known claustrophobia, etc.), pregnancy, and evidence or history of cardiovascular disease. A total of 345 adolescents met the inclusion criteria and were invited to participate through printed and email invitation letters sent to them and their parents or caregivers (**Figure 2**). Approximately 43% of them showed interest and were thus invited to virtual meetings throughout the first quarter of 2021 in which the study was presented and the investigators and clinicians leading the study answered the questions and doubts. Invitees who verbally agreed to participate were scheduled to attend the imaging facilities at the *Centro Nacional de Investigaciones Cardiovasculares* (CNIC), where informed consent was signed. Among 124 participants who finally gave written informed consent, one was unable to undergo the MR examination due to claustrophobia. The analysis thus included 123 participants (overall response rate ~36%).

The MR scans were performed between March and October 2021, coinciding with the final follow-up (4-year follow-up) of the mentioned trial.

Figure 2. Flow diagram of participants. MR, magnetic resonance; EnIGMA, Early Imaging Markers of unhealthy lifestyles in Adolescents.

After MR was performed, data were individually examined by researchers to identify images acquisition errors before post-processing. Then, 32 studies were excluded from analysis after quality check due to dental prosthesis related artifacts during image acquisition. Moreover, 6 studies did not include specific perfusion sequences due to technical problems. Finally, 91 segmentation studies and 85 perfusion studies were available for the analysis.

3.2 Magnetic resonance imaging acquisition protocol

Brain images were acquired using a 3T Ingenia Elition X scanner (Philips Medical Systems, Best, The Netherlands). Structural 3D T1-weighted images were acquired using the following parameters: TR=3000 ms, TE=4 ms, TI=850 ms, flip angle=8, FOV=250 x 250 x 190 mm³, acquired voxel size=0.9 x 0.9 x 0.9 mm³. Perfusion MRI was conducted using a time encoded pseudo-continuous ASL sequence (te-ASL) featuring the following parameters based on previous studies (15): TR = 4600 ms, TE = 12 ms, flip angle = 90°, FOV = 220 x 220 x 120 mm³, voxel size = 2.29 x 2.29 x 6.0 mm³, 20 slices in ascending order, thickness/gap = 6 mm/0 mm, label duration = 3600 ms divided into sub-boli of 1800, 600, 400, 300, 200, 150, and 150 ms, delay time after labelling = 200 ms, time-encoded factor = 8, Hadamard-8 labelling scheme, scan duration = 5 min 31 s. Participants were instructed to rest with their eyes closed and asked to avoid sleeping or engaging any cognitive activity during the scan. A magnetization equilibrium (M0) 3D image was also acquired using the same parameters as te-ASL, except for TR/TE which was 2000/10 ms. Labelling and background suppression were switched off (scan duration = 14 s).

3.3 Magnetic resonance imaging post-processing

In this study, T1 images served as the basis for volumetric analysis. The post-processing algorithm followed is summarized in **Figure 3**. This analysis utilized as a core the "recon-all" function within the FreeSurfer 6.0.1 software to obtain cortical (Desikan-Killiani parcellations) and subcortical structures (aseg atlas) in native space (**Figure 4**).

Figure 3. Magnetic resonance imaging post-processing plan for volumetry and perfusion analysis.

For the te-ASL image pipeline, a sequence of processing steps was executed using an in-house Python code and the FSL 6.0.5.1 software. These steps, which included motion correction by the MCFLIRT FSL function and Hadamard decoding, aimed at generating multi-PLD data. The Bayesian Inference for Arterial Spin Labeling (BASIL) toolbox from the FSL (<https://fsl.fmrib.ox.ac.uk/fsl/fslwiki/BASIL>) was employed to generate CBF maps from the fitting of the multi-PLD data, 3D T1, and M0 images. Finally, co-

registration of the T1-weighted segmentations to the CBF map space was performed to enable perfusion measurements in the original resolution of te-ASL.

Figure 4. A: Sagittal, axial and coronal view of MRI after cortical and subcortical segmentation by FreeSurfer 6.0.1 software. B: axial cuts of a perfusion map and T1-weighted sequence.

Moreover, to assess regional differences through a voxel-wise statistical analysis, normalized CBF maps were co-registered to MNI space using the Statistical Parametric Mapping software (SPM12: <https://www.fil.ion.ucl.ac.uk/spm/>). Then, maps in MNI space will be smoothed with a Gaussian kernel of 12 mm FWHM.

After this process, from each MR study we will obtain a volume value for 138 different anatomical regions and a perfusion value for 111 regions, as well as a common CBF map grouping the perfusion information from the 85 available studies.

3.4 Cardiovascular health assessment during follow-up

CVH will be assessed based on the recent Life's Essential 8 score endorsed by the AHA (16). However, bearing in mind that the focus of the present study is to determine the effect of lifestyle on MR parameters, only lifestyle-related factors will be considered as initial approach. Thus, we will use a modified Life's Essential 8 score including the following 5 variables: diet, physical activity (PA), nicotine exposure, sleep health and BMI. Each CVH metric ranged from 0 to 100 points, with a higher score indicating a better CVH profile. As a continuous variable, each participant's overall CVH modified Life's Essential 8 score thus ranged from 0 to 100 points (the mean of the five variables will be used, as recommended). As stated previously, CVH was assessed in 3 time points: baseline, 2-year follow-up and 4-year follow-up. For the present study, the cumulative effect of CVH over the entire follow-up will be considered as the exposure variable. In order to assess the modified Life's Essential 8 score in each time-point, the included CVH metrics were measured as explained below.

3.4.1 Diet

To assess changes in diet and adherence to the Mediterranean diet in adolescents, a validated 157-item semi-quantitative food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) was used (17). This questionnaire will allow us to calculate 14-point Mediterranean Diet Adherence Screener (MEDAS) (18). In the original Life's Essential 8 score this metric is assessed

using the Mediterranean Eating Pattern for Americans (MEPA) score (16). However, we decided to use the MEDAS score as our population sample is based on a Mediterranean country (Spain). Then the MEDAS score was adapted to 13 points, excluding wine, providing the following score categorization:

13-12 MEDAS points -> 100 points.

11-10 MEDAS points -> 80 points.

9-7 MEDAS points -> 50 points.

6-4 MEDAS points -> 25 points.

3-0 MEDAS points -> 0 points.

3.4.2 Physical activity

Time spent in moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (MVPA) was estimated with an Actigraph wGT3X-BT accelerometer for 7 consecutive days at each time-point. Records were considered valid if they provided data from a minimum of four consecutive or non-consecutive days, with at least 600 min per day of worn time. The MVPA will be calculated according to specific cutoff points for adolescence (19). If accelerometry was unavailable, the QAPACE survey (*Quantification de L'Activité Physique en Altitude chez les Enfants*) self-reporting method was used (17). The score for this metric will be assigned as described in the Life's Essential 8 score (16).

3.4.3 Nicotine exposure

Nicotine exposure was assessed with a standard questionnaire (20). Adolescents who reported never having smoked tobacco products (cigarettes, e-cigarettes, or hookah) scored 100 points; if they have tried tobacco products but they do not currently smoke

scored 50 points and a value of 0 was assigned if they have tried tobacco products and currently smoke. A value of 20 points was subtracted (unless the score is 0) for living with active indoor smoker at home.

3.4.4 Sleep health

Sleep was assessed with the same accelerometer (Actigraph wGT3X-BT) placed on the participant's non-dominant wrist for seven consecutive days, 24 h a day. Records were considered valid if they provided data from at least four consecutive or non-consecutive days of worn time with a maximum of 960 min of sleep per 24 h. Sleep duration was determined using Cole–Kripke cutoff points (21,22) and the score for this metric will be assigned as described in the Life's Essential 8 score (16).

3.4.5 Body mass index

Body weight was measured with an OMRON BF511 electronic scale and height with a Seca 213 portable stadiometer, with the participant wearing light clothes and no shoes. BMI was calculated at each time-point as body weight divided by height squared (kg/m^2). Age- and sex-adjusted BMI z-scores and percentiles will be calculated according to Centres for Disease Control standards (23). The score for this metric will be assigned as described in the Life's Essential 8 score (16).

3.5 Emotional state assessment

Emotional state assessment was based in two domains that were evaluated in each timepoint as follow:

3.5.1 Self-esteem

Self-esteem was estimated using the subscale Child Health and Illness Profile-Adolescent Edition (CHIP-AE), validated for Spanish population (24). The score at CHIP-AE varies from 1 to 20, with a higher score indicating a better self-esteem.

3.5.2 Mood

The questionnaire used in *Vazquez-Fernandez et al.2013 (25)* to assess mood in a group of Spanish adolescents was also utilized in the present study. Negative mood is considered when answering “*always*” or “*often*” at ≥ 3 items. Therefore, “*always*” and “*often*” answers are marked as 1 point, whereas the rest are marked as 0 points. The final value in the questionnaire is 0-6.

4 Data Analysis

All data related to the assessment of CVH throughout the 4-year follow-up has been prospectively collected in a web-based case report form (CRF) specifically designed for the trial. However, all data obtained specifically for the EnIGMA study, mainly MR data and concomitant sociodemographic and anthropometric data, have been collected using the REDCap electronic data capture tool hosted at the CNIC.

Statistical analysis will be performed with Stata software version 16 or higher (StataCorp, College Station, Texas) and the Statistical Parametric Mapping software. The second one will be used specifically for the voxel-wise statistical analysis. The entire statistical code will be written by four authors (MG-C, RP, CR and JM-G). The principal investigator (RF-J) and statistical expert (AdG) will perform a review at the statistical programming code level, as well as on the report level.

4.1 Outcomes or dependent variables

To detect early cerebral subclinical changes in adolescents, a battery of volumetry and perfusion MR-derived parameters will be considered as outcomes. To evaluate these changes, some global brain measures for perfusion and volumetry were selected based on their relation to CVH in previous studies (4,5,26). Considering physiological variability in brain measurements depending on age, physical development and sex (27,28), a statistical analysis adjusted by these variables will be performed. Physical and sexual development will be assessed as stage in Tanner scale (29) (ordinal variable grading maturation state from 1 to 5) around MR acquisition time (at last trial follow-up of participants).

Furthermore, volumetry variables will be expressed as a ratio to estimated total intracranial volume (eTIV), following the model employed in previous studies (6). The purpose of indexing these variables is to attempt to mitigate differences due to body surface area and the impact of growth during childhood. Listed below are the MR variables chosen as outcomes:

Volumetry variables (mm³):

- Total brain volume (TBV).
- Grey matter volume (GMV).
- White matter volume (WMV).

Volumetry variables will be expressed as raw variables (mm³) as well as a ratio to eTIV.

Perfusion variables (mL/100g/min):

- Cerebral blood flow (CBF).
- White matter perfusion (WMP).
- Grey matter perfusion (GMP).

4.2 Independent variables

The main independent variable will be the modified Life's Essential 8 score, the CHIP-AE score and mood-assessment validated score. Modified Life's Essential 8 score is composed by five metrics, as assessed in the three time-points (baseline, 2-year follow-up and 4-year follow-up), ranging from 0 to 100 points (the mean of the five variables will be used, as recommended).

The individual CVH metrics will be assessed as well as continuous raw measurement:

- Diet assessed as MEDAS score (points).

- Physical activity (MVPA in min/day)
- Sleep health (hours/day).
- BMI as standardized percentile (30).

However, nicotine exposure will not be expressed as a continuous variable but instead as a categorical one, based on a standard questionnaire, according to information in 3.4.3.

Mood evaluation will be included as a continuous variable punctuated from 0-6 as described in *Vazquez-Fernandez et al. (25)*.

Self-esteem, assessed by CHIP-AE score, will be included also as a continuous variable ranged between 1 and 20.

4.3 Analysis method

The final statistical analysis will be performed when the study is completely analysed, including all the imaging examinations. No interim analysis will be performed.

A 2-sided p-value of 0.05 will be considered statistically significant. There will be no formal adjustment of p-values for multiple testing. Continuous variables will be presented as means \pm standard deviation (SD), and categorical variables will be presented as frequencies and percentages, unless otherwise specified.

The reporting of this study will adhere to the Strengthening The Reporting of Observational studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) guideline for observational studies (31).

Missing values in the covariates, if any, will not be imputed. The modified Life's Essential 8 score will be calculated only in participants with valid values in at least 4 of the 5 CVH individual metrics included at the corresponding time-point. For participants

with 1 missing individual health metrics, the overall CVH will be calculated as the mean of the remaining metrics normalized to 100 points.

The cumulative effect will be assessed only in those participants that have available data for at least 2 out of the 3 time-points for each independent variable (CVH score or each CVH individual metric).

The null hypothesis is that there is no relation between the effect of unhealthy lifestyles and negative emotional state (cumulative and in the last time-point) and early subclinical changes in cerebral volumetry and perfusion detected by advanced MR imaging. The alternative hypothesis is based on the existence of association between them.

To evaluate the relation between emotional and CV health, the statistical analysis will be divided into two levels of complexity, a general regions-based one and a specific voxel-based one.

4.3.1 Regions-based analysis

The regions-based analysis will evaluate the association between cumulative CV and emotional health over the course of adolescence and at the last time-point (as independent variables) and the MR parameters described above (as dependent continuous variables).

The independent variables (overall CVH, individual CVH and emotional health metrics) were assessed in three time-points, while the dependent variables (MR volumetry

and perfusion parameters) were assessed at the last (4-year) follow-up, concurrent with the last CVH assessment. The cumulative effect of the independent variables will be assessed using the area under the curve (AUC) method. AUC represents an average over time and can accommodate short-term fluctuation of individuals, thus being an ideal method to analyse the present study's data (32). AUC will be calculated as the integral of the curve parameters during the follow-up period in each subject, including then the three timepoints. To facilitate interpretation, the AUC values will be divided by the years of follow-up of the participants. Stata command *integ* will be used for AUC calculations.

Considering the objective of the study, different approaches will be carried out as stated below, using linear regression models. Different steps for analysis will be performed:

1. Data exploration. For visually assessing the distribution of variables, dot plots and boxplots will be used for continuous variables whereas bar graphs will be used for categorical variables.
2. Unadjusted univariable linear regression models. As dependent variable/outcome, the brain MR parameters will be used. As independent variable, the following will be used:
 - a. Modified overall Life's Essential 8 score, either as AUC representing the cumulative effect or the value of the modified overall Life's Essential 8 score at final follow-up.
 - b. Each individual health metric handled as described in 4.2, either as cumulative effect (AUC) or the value at final follow-up. In the case of categorized individual health metrics, the reference group will be the "high" (healthiest) category.

- c. Emotional health variables, as described in 4.2.
3. Adjusted multivariable linear regression models.
- a. Dependent variable. The dependent variables will be the different MR parameters.
 - b. Independent variables.
 - i. All variables specified for the unadjusted model will be included.
 - ii. With the aim of evaluating the effect of different CVH metric by itself, all individual CVH parameters will be used separately.
 - iii. Adjustment by age (continuous variable), sex (binary variable) and sexual development expressed as stage in Tanner scale (29) (ordinal variable graded from 1 to 5), will be performed. This adjustment aim to minimize differences related to physiological development of adolescents (27,28).

As sensitivity analyses, we will obtain the mean of the independent variables throughout the three timepoints of the study. We will replicate the analysis described previously using the same adjustment covariates.

4.3.2 Voxel-based analysis

In the second level analysis, we will perform a voxel-wise analysis of differences in cerebral blood flow associated to emotional and CV health patterns, with all MR images registered into a common anatomical space. Then, specific contrasts will be defined to test the correlation between CBF and CV and emotional health variables (modified Life's

Essential 8 score, the five metrics included in modified Life's Essential 8 score individually, CHIP-AE, and mood-assessing questionnaire) correcting by age and gender. Family-Wise Error (FEW) corrections at $p < 0.05$ were applied to adjust for multiple comparisons.

For all analysis, further by-gender stratification will be considered. Because smaller subgroups size is expected using this approach, the absolute value for the strength of association/correlation between independent and dependent variables will be considered for results interpretation rather than the p-value alone.

5 Acknowledgement

This project is funded by the Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII) and co-funded by the European Union (grants PI19/01704 and PI22/01560). The CNIC is supported by the ISCIII, the Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades, and the Pro CNIC Foundation, and is a Severo Ochoa Center of Excellence (grant CEX2020-001041-S funded by MICIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033).

6 References

1. Yusuf S, Joseph P, Rangarajan S, Islam S, Mente A, Hystad P, et al. Modifiable risk factors, cardiovascular disease, and mortality in 155 722 individuals from 21 high-income, middle-income, and low-income countries (PURE): a prospective cohort study. *Lancet Lond Engl*. 2020 Mar 7;395(10226):795–808.
2. Livingston G, Sommerlad A, Orgeta V, Costafreda SG, Huntley J, Ames D, et al. Dementia prevention, intervention, and care. *The Lancet*. 2017 Dec 16;390(10113):2673–734.
3. Huang LY, Ou YN, Yang YX, Wang ZT, Tan L, Yu JT. Associations of cardiovascular risk factors and lifestyle behaviors with neurodegenerative disease: a Mendelian randomization study. *Transl Psychiatry*. 2023 Jul 24;13(1):267.
4. Friedman JI, Tang CY, de Haas HJ, Changchien L, Goliash G, Dabas P, et al. Brain Imaging Changes Associated With Risk Factors for Cardiovascular and Cerebrovascular Disease in Asymptomatic Patients. *JACC Cardiovasc Imaging*. 2014 Oct 1;7(10):1039–53.
5. Launer LJ, Lewis CE, Schreiner PJ, Sidney S, Battapady H, Jacobs DR, et al. Vascular Factors and Multiple Measures of Early Brain Health: CARDIA Brain MRI Study. *PLOS ONE*. 2015 Mar 26;10(3):e0122138.
6. Hu YH, Halstead MR, Bryan RN, Schreiner PJ, Jacobs DR, Sidney S, et al. Association of Early Adulthood 25-Year Blood Pressure Trajectories With Cerebral Lesions and Brain Structure in Midlife. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2022 Mar 1;5(3):e221175.
7. Rovio SP, Pahkala K, Nevalainen J, Juonala M, Salo P, Kähönen M, et al. Cardiovascular Risk Factors From Childhood and Midlife Cognitive Performance: The Young Finns Study. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2017 May 9;69(18):2279–89.
8. Wolters FJ, Zonneveld HI, Hofman A, van der Lugt A, Koudstaal PJ, Vernooij MW, et al. Cerebral Perfusion and the Risk of Dementia: A Population-Based Study. *Circulation*. 2017 Aug 22;136(8):719–28.
9. Xiong Y, Chen RS, Wang XY, Li X, Dai LQ, Yu RQ. Cerebral blood flow in adolescents with drug-naive, first-episode major depressive disorder: An arterial spin labeling study based on voxel-level whole-brain analysis. *Front Neurosci*. 2022 Jul 27;16:966087.
10. Ho TC, Wu J, Shin DD, Liu TT, Tapert SF, Yang G, et al. Altered Cerebral Perfusion in Executive, Affective, and Motor Networks During Adolescent Depression. *J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry*. 2013 Oct;52(10):10.1016/j.jaac.2013.07.008.
11. Lloyd-Jones DM, Ning H, Labarthe D, Brewer L, Sharma G, Rosamond W, et al. Status of Cardiovascular Health in US Adults and Children Using the American Heart Association’s New “Life’s Essential 8” Metrics: Prevalence Estimates From the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES), 2013 Through 2018. *Circulation*. 2022 Sep 13;146(11):822–35.

10. Fernandez-Jimenez R, Santos-Beneit G, de Cos-Gandoy A, Fernández-Alvira JM, Tresserra-Rimbau A, Storniolo C, et al. Prevalence and correlates of cardiovascular health among early adolescents enrolled in the SI! Program in Spain: a cross-sectional analysis. *Eur J Prev Cardiol.* 2022 Jan 1;29(1):e7–10.
13. Fernandez-Jimenez R, Santos-Beneit G, Tresserra-Rimbau A, Bodega P, de Miguel M, de Cos-Gandoy A, et al. Rationale and design of the school-based SI! Program to face obesity and promote health among Spanish adolescents: A cluster-randomized controlled trial. *Am Heart J.* 2019 Sep;215:27–40.
14. Santos-Beneit G, Fernández-Alvira JM, Tresserra-Rimbau A, Bodega P, de Cos-Gandoy A, de Miguel M, et al. School-Based Cardiovascular Health Promotion in Adolescents: A Cluster Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA Cardiol.* 2023 Sep 1;8(9):816–24.
15. Falcon C, Montesinos P, Václavů L, Kassinosopoulos M, Minguillon C, Fauria K, et al. Time-encoded ASL reveals lower cerebral blood flow in the early AD continuum. *Alzheimers Dement J Alzheimers Assoc.* 2024 Aug;20(8):5183–97.
16. Lloyd-Jones DM, Allen NB, Anderson CAM, Black T, Brewer LC, Foraker RE, et al. Life's Essential 8: Updating and Enhancing the American Heart Association's Construct of Cardiovascular Health: A Presidential Advisory From the American Heart Association. *Circulation.* 2022 Aug 2;146(5):e18–43.
17. Fernández-Ballart JD, Piñol JL, Zazpe I, Corella D, Carrasco P, Toledo E, et al. Relative validity of a semi-quantitative food-frequency questionnaire in an elderly Mediterranean population of Spain. *Br J Nutr.* 2010 Jun;103(12):1808–16.
18. Schröder H, Fitó M, Estruch R, Martínez-González MA, Corella D, Salas-Salvadó J, et al. A Short Screener Is Valid for Assessing Mediterranean Diet Adherence among Older Spanish Men and Women. *J Nutr.* 2011 Jun 1;141(6):1140–5.
19. Chandler JL, Brazendale K, Beets MW, Mealing BA. Classification of physical activity intensities using a wrist-worn accelerometer in 8–12-year-old children. *Pediatr Obes.* 2016;11(2):120–7.
20. Moreno C, Ramos P, Rivera F, Jiménez-Iglesias A, García-Moya I, Sánchez-Queija I, et al. Las conductas relacionadas con la salud y el desarrollo de los adolescentes españoles. Resultados del estudio HBSC-2010 con chicos y chicas españoles de 11 a 18 años. *Minist Sanid Serv Soc E Igual.* 2012;916p.
21. Cole RJ, Kripke DF, Gruen W, Mullaney DJ, Gillin JC. Automatic sleep/wake identification from wrist activity. *Sleep.* 1992 Oct;15(5):461–9.
22. Kripke DF, Hahn EK, Grizas AP, Wadiak KH, Loving RT, Poceta JS, et al. Wrist actigraphic scoring for sleep laboratory patients: algorithm development. *J Sleep Res.* 2010 Dec;19(4):612–9.
23. Fryar CD, Carroll MD, Gu Q, Afful J, Ogden CL. Anthropometric Reference Data for Children and Adults: United States, 2015-2018. *Vital Health Stat 3.* 2021 Jan;(36):1–44.

24. Rajmil L, Serra-Sutton V, Alonso J, Starfield B, Riley AW, Vázquez JR, et al. The Spanish version of the Child Health and Illness Profile-Adolescent Edition (CHIP-AE). *Qual Life Res Int J Qual Life Asp Treat Care Rehabil*. 2003 May;12(3):303–13.
25. Vázquez Fernández ME, Muñoz Moreno MF, Fierro Urturi A, Alfaro González M, Rodríguez Molinero L, Bustamante Marcos P. Estado de ánimo de los adolescentes y su relación con conductas de riesgo y otras variables. *Pediatría Aten Primaria*. 2013 Sep;15(59):e75–84.
26. Salvan P, Wassenaar T, Wheatley C, Beale N, Cottaar M, Papp D, et al. Multimodal Imaging Brain Markers in Early Adolescence Are Linked with a Physically Active Lifestyle. *J Neurosci Off J Soc Neurosci*. 2021 Feb 3;41(5):1092–104.
27. Satterthwaite TD, Shinohara RT, Wolf DH, Hopson RD, Elliott MA, Vandekar SN, et al. Impact of puberty on the evolution of cerebral perfusion during adolescence. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2014 Jun 10;111(23):8643–8.
28. Biagi L, Abbruzzese A, Bianchi MC, Alsop DC, Del Guerra A, Tosetti M. Age dependence of cerebral perfusion assessed by magnetic resonance continuous arterial spin labeling. *J Magn Reson Imaging JMRI*. 2007 Apr;25(4):696–702.
29. Emmanuel M, Bokor BR. Tanner Stages. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 [cited 2024 Jul 17]. Available from: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470280/>
30. Fryar CD, Kruszon-Moran D, Gu Q, Carroll M, Ogden CL. Mean Body Weight, Height, Waist Circumference, and Body Mass Index Among Children and Adolescents: United States, 1999-2018. *Natl Health Stat Rep*. 2021 Aug;(160):1–24.
31. von Elm E, Altman DG, Egger M, Pocock SJ, Gøtzsche PC, Vandenbroucke JP, et al. The Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) statement: guidelines for reporting observational studies. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2008 Apr;61(4):344–9.
32. Cook NR, Rosner BA, Chen W, Srinivasan SR, Berenson GS. Using the area under the curve to reduce measurement error in predicting young adult blood pressure from childhood measures. *Stat Med*. 2004;23(22):3421–35.